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Carbon Footprint Disclosures And Financial Performance Of Listed Healthcare Firms In Nigeria

Benjamin Etim Elensi; Dr. Emmanuel O. Emenyi* & Dr. Sunday A. Okpo

Department Of Accounting,
Akwa Ibom State University, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
*emmanuelemenyi@aksu.edu.ng and emenyi007@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The absence of carbon footprint disclosures in the Nigerian healthcare sector has not only hindered the sector's ability to contribute to national and global efforts to mitigate climate change but also poses significant risks to the financial performance and long-term sustainability of healthcare firms. In view of this, the study carefully examined the effect of carbon footprint disclosures on financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. *Ex-post facto* research design was adopted, and panel data covering ten (10) years period, that is (2014-2023) were collected across seven (7) listed healthcare firms in Nigeria which also formed the sample size of the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and panel multiple regression analysis via E-views 10.0 statistical package. However, the study's findings revealed that Capital intensity disclosure has a significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.096837 {0.1393}) with return on assets of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, Energy consumption disclosure has a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030615 {0.7908}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, Carbon offset disclosure has a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030169 {0.0629}) with return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria while Renewable energy usage disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.070139 {0.0022}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. It also revealed that Supply chain emission disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.1716 {0.0069}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. Conclusively, the study underscores the importance of strategic environmental disclosures and sustainable practices in improving financial performance. The study recommended amongst others, that Healthcare firms in Nigeria should focus on reducing their carbon intensity by adopting cleaner energy sources and improving operational efficiencies and financial performance.

Keywords: Carbon footprint disclosures, financial performance, return on asset

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Carbon footprint disclosures is the practice of companies or organizations publicly reporting the total amount of greenhouse gas emissions, typically measured in carbon dioxide equivalents (CO₂e), that are directly or indirectly produced as a result of their business activities. Carbon footprint disclosures aim to increase transparency, accountability, and awareness regarding an organization's carbon emissions, also thereby fostering environmentally responsible practices and facilitating informed decision-making by stakeholders (Akpan & Simeon, 2021). A growing concern for environmental sustainability and the impact of business operations on the environment has led to an increased focus on carbon footprint disclosures by companies globally (Simeon et al., 2024). In recent years, stakeholders have become more interested in understanding how companies manage their environmental impact, leading to a surge in research examining the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance (Samuel et al., 2024).

Healthcare firms offers vital roles in society by providing essential services that directly affect public health and well-being. In Nigeria, listed healthcare firms are under increasing pressure to not only deliver quality healthcare services but also to demonstrate their commitment to environmental sustainability as postulated by Emenyi (2024)¹. As such, investigating the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and the financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria is pertinent to understanding the broader implications of environmental reporting in a developing economy context. The independent variables examined in this study include carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, and carbon offset disclosure, while return on asset represents the dependent variable.

Through exploring the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance within the context of listed healthcare firms, this study seeks to contribute to the existing literature on corporate sustainability reporting and its implications for firm performance as seen in Emenyi, (2024)². Emenyi, and Okpokpo, (2023) x-rayed that understanding how environmental disclosures influence financial outcomes in the healthcare sector can offer valuable insights for investors, regulators, and policymakers seeking to promote sustainable business practices. Moreover, the findings of this study may inform strategic decision-making within healthcare firms, guiding them towards more environmentally responsible practices that benefit both their financial performance and broader societal well-being.

Statement of the problem

Unfortunately, the increasing awareness of climate change and its devastating impacts on the environment and human health has led to growing concerns about the role of businesses in mitigating these effects. The healthcare sector is a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions, primarily due to its energy-intensive operations and supply chain activities. Despite this, there is a lack of transparency and accountability in the healthcare sector regarding its environmental impact, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria as reported by Udomah, and Emenyi, (2023). Friske et al., (2023) stated that in Nigeria, the healthcare sector is dominated by private hospitals and healthcare companies, many of which are listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. While these companies are required to disclose certain financial and non-financial information, there is no specific requirement for them to disclose their carbon footprint or environmental impact. This lack of transparency makes it difficult for stakeholders, including investors, regulators, and patients, to assess the environmental sustainability of these companies and make informed decisions (Ukpe, et al., 2024).

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the effect of carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. This was carefully achieved through the following specific objectives:

1. To analyze the effect of carbon intensity disclosure on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
2. To investigate the effect of energy consumption disclosure on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
3. To appraise the effect of carbon offset disclosure on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
4. To ascertain the effect of renewable energy usage disclosure on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
5. To evaluate the effect of supply chain emission disclosure on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Carbon footprint disclosure

Carbon footprint disclosure is a critical component of environmental reporting, which has gained significant attention in recent years due to the escalating concerns about climate change (Friske et al., 2023). At its core, carbon footprint disclosure refers to the process of measuring, reporting, and verifying the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with an organization's activities. This includes emissions from direct operations, such as energy consumption and transportation, as well as indirect emissions from supply chains, product use, and end-of-life product disposal (Fizzah, 2023).

Ukpe, et. al, (2024), opined that by disclosing their carbon footprint, organizations provide stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of their environmental impact, enabling informed decision-making and promoting accountability.

The importance of carbon footprint disclosure cannot be overstated, particularly in the context of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. As the healthcare sector continues to grow and expand, its environmental footprint is likely to increase, contributing to climate change and its associated health risks as stated by Emeny (2024)¹. Mirrale and Redono, (2021) quoted that through disclosing their carbon footprint, healthcare firms can identify areas for improvement, reduce their environmental impact, and mitigate climate-related risks. Emenyi, (2024)² added that carbon footprint disclosure can also have financial implications, as investors and stakeholders increasingly consider environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors in their investment decisions. Elsayed, (2023) postulated that prioritizing carbon footprint disclosure, listed healthcare firms in Nigeria can demonstrate their commitment to sustainability, enhance their reputation, and ultimately drive long-term financial performance.

2.1.1.1 Carbon intensity disclosure

Carbon intensity disclosure involves reporting the amount of carbon emissions associated with a company's operations, relative to its economic output. Chen et al., (2023) defined Carbon intensity disclosure as the process of disclosing information about a company's carbon intensity, which is a measure of the amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions generated per unit of production, revenue, or other business metric. Carbon intensity disclosure is a crucial aspect of environmental reporting that provides stakeholders with insight into the relative carbon emissions produced by an organization in relation to its level of output or activity (Widianto & Sari, 2020). By calculating and disclosing carbon intensity, companies can demonstrate their commitment to reducing their carbon footprint in proportion to their operations, facilitating comparisons between different organizations and sectors as documented by Emenyi, and Okpokpo, (2023).

This metric not only helps to track progress towards emission reduction targets but also encourages companies to adopt more sustainable practices and technologies to improve their operational efficiency and environmental performance (Adeyemi & Ayanlola, 2015). Through transparent carbon intensity disclosure, businesses can showcase their efforts in transitioning to a lower-carbon economy and aligning with global sustainability goals, ultimately driving positive change towards a more environmentally friendly future (Pratiwi et al., 2021).

2.1.1.2 Energy consumption disclosure

Energy consumption disclosure is a critical aspect of environmental reporting, which involves the transparent and accurate disclosure of a company's energy usage patterns. Rokhmawati et al., (2015) stated that in healthcare firms in Nigeria, energy consumption disclosure is essential as it provides stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of the company's energy footprint, including the types and amounts of energy consumed, as well as the associated greenhouse gas emissions. Egbunike and Odumodu, (2021) reported that through disclosing their energy consumption patterns, healthcare firms can demonstrate their commitment to environmental sustainability, reduce their energy costs, and mitigate climate-related risks. Moreover, energy consumption disclosure can also help healthcare firms to identify areas for improvement, optimize their energy usage, and invest in energy-efficient technologies.

According to Loan et al., (2024), the importance of energy consumption disclosure cannot be overstated, particularly in the healthcare sector where energy-intensive medical equipment and facilities are ubiquitous. In Nigeria, the healthcare sector is heavily reliant on fossil fuels, which contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change as postulated by Okafor et al., (2022) alongside Gianni et al., (2022). By disclosing their energy consumption patterns, listed healthcare firms in Nigeria can provide stakeholders with a clear understanding of their environmental impact, enabling informed decision-making and promoting accountability (Emmanuel et al., 2023).

2.1.1.3 Carbon offset disclosure

Carbon offset disclosure is the transparent reporting of greenhouse gas emissions by an organization and the efforts taken to compensate for these emissions through environmentally friendly projects. Carbon offset disclosure is a crucial aspect of sustainability reporting for organizations aiming to mitigate their environmental impact (Yan et al., 2019). It involves the transparent and detailed

reporting of the amount of greenhouse gas emissions generated by an entity and the measures taken to counterbalance these emissions through environmentally friendly projects such as reforestation, renewable energy investments, or energy efficiency initiatives (Al-Mari & Mardini, 2024). In the phase of healthcare firms in Nigeria, carbon offset disclosure plays a significant role in showcasing a firm's commitment to environmental stewardship and corporate social responsibility (Benson et al., 2021; Sumiati et al., 2021).

Liu, (2017) added that voluntarily disclosing their carbon offset initiatives, these firms not only demonstrate transparency and accountability to stakeholders, but also enhance their reputation and credibility in the eyes of investors, consumers, and regulators. Furthermore, carbon offset disclosure can potentially lead to cost savings for healthcare firms by promoting energy efficiency measures and reducing operational expenses associated with carbon-intensive activities (Luo et al., 2012).

2.1.1.4 Renewable energy usage disclosure

Renewable energy usage disclosure means businesses or organisations tell truthfully how much of their energy comes from sources like solar, wind, hydro or biomass. This disclosure shows whether power used is clean or from fossil fuels. New global rules require firms to state percentages of energy used from grid electricity plus percentage from renewable sources (IFRS S2 climate-related standards). IFRS S2 requires that companies disclose the share of energy used that is renewable relative to total energy consumption. Such transparency helps people see whether companies are serious about lowering pollution, protecting environment and meeting climate goals (Al-Mari & Mardini, 2024). Recently the Global Reporting Initiative released new standards called GRI 102 Climate Change plus GRI 103 Energy that set out how companies must report their energy usage including amounts of renewable energy usage, targets to move away from fossil fuels plus progress made. These standards will take effect for reporting years starting in 2027 (Benson et al., 2021; Sumiati et al., 2021).

2.1.1.5 Supply chain emission disclosure

Supply chain emission disclosure means that businesses report how much pollution comes not just from their own factories or offices but also from outside sources such as suppliers, transport of materials, use of products, waste generation (Widianto & Sari, 2020). These outside emissions are often called "Scope 3 emissions." Many companies still do not disclose Scope 3 emissions even though they are usually the biggest share of a company's climate footprint. A recent report by CDP shows almost 60 percent of companies did not report any supply chain emissions in 2022. Rules and standards are pushing firms toward full disclosure (Fizzah, 2023). The GHG Protocol is updating its Scope 3 Standard so more companies follow similar ways of measuring emissions across supply chains. In India, the Securities and Exchange Board has redefined what value chain partners are for listed firms so companies must include emissions from suppliers that make up a certain part of their purchases or sales (Emenyi, & Okpokpo, 2023).

2.1.2 Financial performance

Financial performance is a multifaceted concept that encompasses various metrics and indicators used to assess a company's financial health, profitability, and growth prospects. In the context of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, financial performance is critical as it reflects the company's ability to generate revenue, manage costs, and create value for shareholders (Freeman, 1984). Financial performance is often evaluated using various metrics, including profitability ratios, such as return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA), efficiency ratios, such as asset turnover and inventory turnover, and market-based metrics, such as stock price and market capitalization (Mardini & Elleuch, 2022). These metrics provide stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of a company's financial performance, enabling them to make informed decisions about investments, creditworthiness, and other business relationships as postulated by Emenyi., & Okpokpo, (2023).

The financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria is influenced by a complex array of factors, including regulatory changes, demographic trends, technological advancements, and shifting patient needs as stated by Makan and Kabra, (2021). In this context, companies that prioritize financial performance are better positioned to navigate these challenges, capitalize on emerging opportunities, and drive long-term growth and sustainability. Moreover, financial performance is closely intertwined with carbon footprint disclosure, as companies that prioritize sustainability and environmental responsibility are often better positioned to manage risks, reduce costs, and drive

innovation (Nurlis, 2019). By examining the relationship between carbon footprint disclosure and financial performance, this study aims to provide insights into the financial implications of environmental sustainability and the role of carbon footprint disclosure in driving long-term financial success (Widiyanto & Sari, 2020).

2.1.2.1 Return on asset

Return on assets (ROA) is a financial metric used to evaluate a company's efficiency in generating profits from its total asset base. It is calculated by dividing the company's net income by its average total assets. ROA provides valuable insights into how effectively a company is utilizing its assets to generate earnings, serving as a key indicator of operational performance and profitability. Cheska et al., (2022) documented that a high ROA indicates that a company is efficient in using its assets to generate profits, while a low ROA suggests that the company may not be effectively leveraging its assets to maximize returns. Okktari and Husnatarina, (2016) carefully added that by analyzing ROA over time, investors and stakeholders can assess the company's ability to generate profits relative to its asset base, providing important information for decision-making and financial analysis.

ROA is particularly useful for comparing companies within the same industry or sector, as it allows for a standardized assessment of how efficiently different companies are utilizing their assets to generate returns as reported by Nurlis, (2019). This metric enables investors to evaluate the relative performance of companies with differing asset sizes and structures, providing a more accurate basis for comparison and investment decision-making as x-rayed by Elsayed, (2023).

2.1.3 Carbon footprint disclosure and return on asset (ROA)

The nexus between carbon footprint disclosures and return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms is a complex and multifaceted one. On one hand, carbon footprint disclosures can have a positive impact on ROA by enhancing a company's reputation and brand value as opined by Benson et al., (2023) alongside Amosun and Akintoye, (2021). When healthcare firms disclose their carbon footprint, they demonstrate their commitment to environmental sustainability and social responsibility, which can lead to increased customer loyalty, improved stakeholder relationships, and enhanced brand reputation (Al-Waeli et al., 2021). This, in turn, can drive business growth, increase revenue, and ultimately improve ROA. Moreover, carbon footprint disclosures can also help healthcare firms to identify areas of inefficiency and waste, leading to cost savings and improved operational efficiency, which can also contribute to improved ROA (Budiono & Dura, 2021).

Issa (2024) argued that carbon footprint disclosures can also have a negative impact on ROA, particularly if the disclosures reveal significant environmental impacts or risks. For example, if a healthcare firm's carbon footprint disclosure reveals high levels of greenhouse gas emissions, it may face increased regulatory scrutiny, reputational damage, and potential litigation risks, all of which can negatively impact ROA. Effendi, (2021) supported that the process of measuring and disclosing carbon footprint can also be costly and time-consuming, which can divert resources away from core business activities and negatively impact ROA. Therefore, the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and ROA of listed healthcare firms is nuanced and depends on various factors, including the company's overall sustainability strategy, the level of environmental risk disclosure, and the effectiveness of its carbon reduction initiatives as x-rayed by (Sumiati et al., 2021).

2.1.3.1 Carbon intensity disclosure and return on asset

Bedi and Singh, (2024) captured that the relationship between carbon intensity disclosure and return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms is an important area of study that sheds light on the impact of environmental sustainability practices on financial performance. Carbon intensity disclosure refers to the extent to which healthcare firms report their greenhouse gas emissions in relation to their operational activities. By disclosing and actively managing their carbon intensity, healthcare firms can enhance their environmental reputation, mitigate regulatory risks, and attract socially responsible investors as stated by Fizzah, (2023). This transparency in environmental reporting can also lead to increased operational efficiency, cost savings, and improved long-term sustainability, all of which can have positive effects on a firm's financial performance and profitability (Bedi & Singh, 2024).

The connection between carbon intensity disclosure and ROA in listed healthcare firms lies in the potential for environmental sustainability practices to drive operational efficiency and value creation (Gianni et al., 2022). Firms that actively disclose and manage their carbon intensity levels are likely to implement energy-efficient practices, reduce waste, and adopt greener technologies, leading to lower

costs and enhanced resource utilization. These efforts can result in improved productivity, reduced operational risks, and increased competitive advantage within the healthcare industry as reviewed by Mirrale and Redono, (2021).

2.1.3.2 Energy consumption disclosure and return on asset

The effect of energy consumption disclosure on the return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria is a crucial area to explore, as it highlights the relationship between energy efficiency practices and financial performance within the healthcare sector as stated by Lu et al., (2021). Energy consumption disclosure involves the transparent reporting of a healthcare firm's energy usage, efficiency measures, and sustainability initiatives. Through actively disclosing their energy consumption data, healthcare firms in Nigeria can effectively communicate their commitment to environmental responsibility, potential cost savings from energy-efficient operations, and compliance with regulatory standards (Rokhmawan et al., 2015). This transparency not only enhances the firm's environmental performance but also signals to investors and stakeholders a proactive approach toward sustainable business practices (Rokhmawan et al., 2015).

The link between energy consumption disclosure and ROA in listed healthcare firms in Nigeria centers on the potential for improved operational efficiency and financial performance (Lu et al., 2021). Firms that disclose their energy consumption data are more likely to implement energy-saving measures, invest in renewable energy sources, and optimize their energy usage, leading to lower operational costs and enhanced asset utilization. These efforts can result in increased profitability, reduced environmental impact, and long-term sustainability for healthcare firms operating in Nigeria as reported by Okafor et al., (2022).

2.1.3.3 Carbon offset disclosure and return on asset

The relationship between carbon offset disclosure and the return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria holds significant implications for both environmental sustainability and financial performance. Carbon offset disclosure involves the transparent reporting of a firm's efforts to offset their carbon emissions through activities such as investing in renewable energy projects, reforestation initiatives, or purchasing carbon credits (Mohammed, 2020). According to Luo et al., (2013), disclosing their carbon offset strategies, healthcare firms in Nigeria can demonstrate their commitment to mitigating climate change, reducing their environmental footprint, and aligning with global sustainability goals. This transparency not only enhances the firm's environmental credibility but also has tangible effects on financial performance as supported by Luo et al., (2012).

Adeyemi and Ayankola, (2015) appraised that investing in carbon offset projects can lead to reduced operating costs, improved resource efficiency, and enhanced brand reputation, ultimately contributing to increased profitability and asset returns for listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. Additionally, by proactively disclosing their carbon offset initiatives, firms can attract environmentally conscious investors, strengthen stakeholder trust, and differentiate themselves in a competitive market, positioning them for long-term success and sustainable growth (Yan et al., 2019; Saka & Oshika, 2014).

2.1.3.4 Renewable energy usage disclosure and return on asset

Renewable energy usage disclosure means that a firm openly reports how much of its power supply comes from clean sources such as sunlight, wind, or water. This act of openness shows how a firm values accountability toward the planet. When companies publish such reports, they build trust among investors who prefer safe, future-focused investments (Widianto & Sari, 2020). Clear disclosure also supports long-term planning that improves internal control, resource management, plus cost reduction. A study by Emmanuel et al. (2023) on Nigerian banks found that renewable energy disclosure helps to improve the image of institutions which later attracts more customers (Yan et al., 2019). This reputation improvement slowly influences their return on assets because more clients prefer firms that act responsibly toward the environment (Benson et al., 2021; Sumiati et al., 2021).

Efficient energy use helps lower expenses, which increases income from existing assets. When a firm replaces expensive fuel sources with cheaper renewable ones, it spends less on electricity or maintenance, meaning its available assets work more effectively (Fizzah, 2023). Firms that share their renewable energy data openly also tend to monitor their consumption better, which supports continuous improvement. Evidence from the University of Nairobi (2024) showed that companies which include renewable energy data in their reports achieve higher return on assets than those that

hide such information. This shows that renewable energy usage disclosure not only supports environmental health but also creates financial strength through better use of resources.

2.1.3.5 Supply chain emission disclosure and return on asset

When companies share information about emissions in their supply chain, they show how much pollution comes from activities outside their own factory walls. Suppliers producing raw materials, transportation of goods, energy used in partners' operations all contribute to these emissions. Cheska et al. (2022) documented that, reporting those supply chain emissions helps stakeholders see the full picture of environmental impact not just what occurs within company sites. A large study "Shareholder value implications of supply chain ESG" found firms with more incidents of bad environmental, social, governance issues among suppliers tend to have lower future ROA, after controlling for current profitability and many other firm features (Chen et al., 2023). That means firms failing to disclose or having poor supply chain environmental behavior risk hurting how well their assets produce profit over time.

Reporting supply chain emissions also helps firms improve asset use efficiency. When disclosure is required or voluntary, firms begin measuring emissions across suppliers which often reveals wasteful operations, poor energy use, excessive transport emissions or weak supplier practices (Al-Mari & Mardini, 2024). By fixing those issues firms reduce costs such as energy bills, transport losses, maintenance or regulatory penalties. A global study "Driving green: Financial benefits of carbon emission reduction in companies" showed that companies that reduce emissions, especially through better supply chain management, achieve higher ROA relative to firms with less attention to emissions (over many countries across many industries) (Driving Green study, 2024). This shows disclosure plus action yield returns on assets over time once firms use their assets more efficiently.

2.2 Theoretical framework

The nexus between carbon footprint disclosure and financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria cannot be ascertained without taking cognizance of some vital theoretical underpinnings. However, in the course of this study, the Stakeholder theory by Edward Freeman in 1984 and Resource-Based view theory by J. Barney in 1991 were reviewed.

2.2.1 The stakeholder theory by Edward Freeman, (1984).

Edward Freeman in 1984 propounded the Stakeholder theory. The theory posits that businesses should consider not only the interests of shareholders but also those of all stakeholders impacted by their operations. Regarding carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance, stakeholder theory suggests that transparent reporting of environmental impact, such as through carbon footprint disclosures, is essential for building trust and maintaining positive relationships with stakeholders. Freeman, (1984) postulated that by disclosing their carbon footprint and outlining strategies to reduce environmental harm, healthcare firms in Nigeria can meet the expectations of various stakeholders who are increasingly concerned about sustainability and corporate responsibility. This proactive approach not only helps in fostering trust and goodwill among stakeholders but can also lead to improved financial performance as also seen in Widiyanto and Sari, (2020).

Freeman, (1984) indicated that by addressing the concerns of stakeholders through carbon footprint disclosures, healthcare firms can enhance their reputation, attract socially responsible investors, and differentiate themselves in the market, thereby potentially boosting their financial performance in the long run (Friske et al., 2023). Thus, the application of stakeholder theory to the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance underscores the importance of considering the broader impacts of business activities on all stakeholders and how aligning with their interests can contribute to both sustainable practices and economic success for listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

2.2.2 The Resource-based view theory by J. Barney, (1991).

The resource-based view (RBV) theory was propounded by J. Barney in 1991. The theory plays a significant role in understanding the relationship between carbon footprint disclosures and financial performance, particularly return on asset (ROA), of listed healthcare firms as recorded by Widiyanto and Sari, (2020). According to Barney (1991), a firm's resources and capabilities are the primary drivers of its sustained competitive advantage. In the context of carbon footprint disclosures, firms that possess resources and capabilities that enable them to effectively manage and disclose their carbon footprint are likely to gain a competitive advantage. This, in turn, can positively impact their financial performance, including ROA.

The significance of the RBV theory to this work lies in its ability to explain how listed healthcare firms can leverage their resources and capabilities to manage and disclose their carbon footprint, ultimately driving financial performance. With RBV theory, this study can provide insights into how firms can develop and utilize their resources and capabilities to achieve sustainability and financial goals. Moreover, the theory can help illustrate how carbon footprint disclosures can become a source of competitive advantage for listed healthcare firms, leading to improved financial performance (Pei Yu et al., 2022).

2.3 Empirical framework

Mamatzakis and Tzouvanas (2025) assessed greenhouse gas emissions and quality of financial reporting: Evidence from the EU. Our study delves into the association between greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the quality of financial reporting. Our investigation focuses on understanding how firms' GHG emissions would impact discretionary accruals and real earnings management. We also test the moderating role of a large board size, and CEO as a board member. Finally, we conduct various robustness checks to ensure the robustness and validity of our findings. We conducted a study on 476 European companies across 17 countries and various industries between 2005 and 2018. We use panel data estimations, and multiple methods to account for emissions and address endogeneity issues in our tests. Our findings indicate that greenhouse gas emissions increase earnings management, as measured through discretionary accruals and real earnings management. This leads to lower quality financial reporting. We also find that a larger board size moderates the relationship between GHG emissions and financial reporting, resulting in greater financial transparency. Our findings provide evidence that firms' GHG emissions, despite stricter emission regulations in the European Union (EU), would be positively associated with real earnings management. This finding calls for more research in different regions to understand if this is a global trend.

Citraningtyas et al. (2025) investigated the impact of greenhouse gas emissions disclosure and institutional ownership on firm value: Evidence from mining industry in Indonesia. In the mining industry, handling and mitigating greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) is crucial to maintaining business and environmental sustainability. A large portion of the world's carbon dioxide emissions come from the mining industry as a result of deforestation and heavy machinery exploration run by fossil fuels in the mining site. This study aims to investigate whether GHG emission reporting, as well as institutionally owned share ownership, would increase the firm's value in the eyes of capital market investors. A panel data regression of the one hundred and sixty-eight listed mining companies on Indonesia's capital market in 2019–2023 reveals that GHG emissions reporting and institutional ownership are likely to increase firm value. The results suggest that investors would value companies with higher GHG emissions and institutional ownership. This study advises mining company management that, although GHG emission mitigation action and reporting and dealing with institutional investors are costly, they will boost company image and value in the capital market.

Abdalla et al. (2025) investigate the effect of audit committee effectiveness (ACE), size of internal audits (IAS), and internal audit outsourcing (IAO) on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions disclosure from the perspectives of stakeholder theory in Malaysia. The current study collected and analyzed data based on 285 observations of plantations listed in Bursa Malaysia from 2016 to 2021. The effects of ACE, IAS, and IAO on the disclosure of GHG emissions are observed using a panel data regression model. The study findings revealed a significant positive relationship between ACE, IAS, and GHG emission disclosure. Based on these results, firms that established an effective audit committee and extended their internal audit teams tended to report more GHG emissions information than other firms. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to consider IAS and IAO when evaluating GHG emissions disclosure. Further, this study assesses firms with higher levels of GHG emissions disclosure using a new global reporting initiative and the Bursa Malaysia Sustainability Reporting Guide based on the GHG emissions disclosure checklist. This expands the existing literature on GHG emission disclosure. The current study may not accurately portray the state of GHG emission disclosure in Malaysia because of its exclusive focus on the plantation sector. As a result, future studies should examine GHG emissions disclosure in other sectors to provide new insights into GHG emissions disclosure in developing countries.

Luu et al. (2025) examined the impact of the mandatory greenhouse gas emissions reporting program (GHGRP) on corporate greenwashing behaviour. Utilising the GHGRP in the United States as a

quasi-natural experiment, we perform a difference-in-difference analysis to a panel dataset of 2731 publicly listed US firms from 2007 to 2022. The data consist of annual observations of firm-level variables, including ESG performance and disclosure metrics, financial characteristics, and environmental innovation indicators. Our results reveal a notable reduction in greenwashing behaviour following the adoption of the GHGRP, suggesting that increased transparency and accountability discourage deceptive disclosure practices. A decomposition analysis shows that the GHGRP motivates firms to improve actual ESG performance while curbing inflated ESG claims. Larger and more profitable firms exhibit a more significant decrease in greenwashing, indicating that those under greater public scrutiny respond more strongly to regulatory oversight. Additionally, firms with higher levels of environmental innovation demonstrate a greater reduction in greenwashing post-GHGRP adoption, reflecting an alignment between sustainability commitments and corporate culture. This study offers valuable insights for firm managers, investors, and policymakers on leveraging the GHGRP framework to promote transparency in corporate reporting practices.

Kilian (2025) carried out an investigation on the disclosure of greenhouse gases by companies: Differences between Africa and the United States of America. On 6 March 2024, the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) proposed and adopted an environmental disclosure rule (Enhancement and Standardisation of Climate-Related Disclosures for Investors). The rule and its explanation consist of 886 pages; consequently, this article attempts to illustrate briefly the environmental metrics or factors that comprise this rule and which US companies have to report on in their audited financial statements. The SEC metrics for calculating and reporting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are largely based on the Greenhouse Gas Protocol and the Task Force on Climate Related Financial Disclosures (TCFD). In Africa, the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) in South Africa has introduced similar environmental metrics for GHG disclosures. In the future, South Africa's Climate Change Bill, 2022, will empower the Minister to issue regulations that promote standardised environmental metrics for companies, similar to the SEC rule. This article also briefly focuses on the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).

Hewagama et al. (2025) aimed to analyse carbon emissions' (CE) impact on New Zealand-listed entities' firm performance before adopting legislation for mandatory climate disclosures. The study uses a fixed effects regression model to examine the impact of CE on Tobin's Q, the return on assets (ROA) and the return on equity (ROE). The sample comprised 97 New Zealand Stock Exchange companies, representing 90% of total market capitalisation. CE are significantly and negatively associated with firm performance, as measured by Tobin's Q (a market-based measure). The negative impact is significant, with an estimated 48.74% decline in the mean Tobin's Q, highlighting the substantial effect of CE on firm valuation. However, CE shows no significant statistical association with the accounting-based measures of ROA or ROE. The results also show that in a voluntary reporting regime, companies disclosing emissions are penalised more with reduced firm value than those that do not disclose. The study serves as a reference point to examine the impact of CE on the firm performance of New Zealand-listed entities before the mandatory climate disclosures came into effect. The results support mandatory disclosure to create transparency and competitiveness in financial markets in relation to CE.

Prasetyaningsih et al. (2025) examined the influence of green accounting and carbon emission disclosure on company value. In the era of globalization and increased awareness of the impacts of climate change, sustainable development has become one of the main concerns at the global level. One of them is the disclosure of carbon emission disclosure and the application of green accounting in the company's operational process as an effort to overcome environmental problems. This study aims to determine whether green accounting & carbon emission disclosure has a positive effect on firm value. The study uses secondary data obtained from annual reports and corporate sustainability reports for the 2019-2023 period. Companies with the energy sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2019-2023 are the criteria for this research data. Data processing using Statistical Package for Social Science. The results showed that the application of green accounting & carbon emission disclosure has no influence on firm value. The ineffectiveness of green accounting and carbon emission disclosure on firm value is likely due to the proxies used in this study that do not fully represent the true indicators of green accounting and carbon emission disclosure. Future research is

recommended to use other proxies that are more relevant in measuring green accounting and disclosure of carbon emissions.

Zhang et al. (2025) investigated the impact of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission disclosure on firm outcomes remains contested, highlighting the need to account for organizational contingencies when evaluating its effects. This study examines how leadership gender diversity—specifically board gender diversity and top management team gender diversity—moderates the relationship between GHG disclosure and firm systematic risk. Using a comprehensive panel of 6966 firm-year observations from 2010 to 2020 and applying robust estimation techniques, we identify gender diversity in leadership as a critical contingent factor. In particular, board gender diversity significantly moderates the GHG disclosure–risk relationship: firms with greater gender diversity in the boardroom experience a stronger risk-reducing effect from both core and extended GHG disclosures, whereas, firms with lower board gender diversity exhibit heightened systematic risk in response to disclosure. These findings contribute to the sustainability literature, resource dependence theory, and upper echelons theory by demonstrating that the impact of environmental disclosure is conditional on leadership composition. The study offers actionable insights for firms seeking to align ESG strategies with governance practices and for investors evaluating the credibility and risk-mitigating potential of corporate sustainability disclosures.

Alkebsee et al. (2025) examined the impact of GHG assurance on firms' carbon emissions performance (CEP) regarding curbing carbon emissions and the effect on such by the GHG assurance provider's affiliation and reputation. It also explores whether the affiliation and reputation of GHG assurance providers imply the relationship between GHG assurance and the firm's CEP. Further, this study examines the moderating effect of the country's development level on the relationship. Based on a sample of international firms from 56 countries spanning the period from 2012 to 2020, this study utilizes the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. We also run the OLS regression at times $t+1$ and $t+2$ to verify the baseline results. To address the endogeneity concerns arising from self-selection bias and the causality effect, this study applies the generalized method of moment (GMM) and the Heckman test. This study finds that GHG assurance leads to better CEP by firms. We also find that engaging with accounting assurance providers leads firms to a better CEP than non-accounting assurance providers. Our results show that Big Four auditors can help firms decrease carbon emissions. We also find that the positive effect of GHG assurance is prevalent in firms operating in developed countries. Our study only considers the influence of the assessor's reputation and affiliation on CEP without examining other factors that may influence the quality of assurance services provided. Our study provides a practical implication related to the influence of a GHG assurance provider's affiliation and reputation globally by providing evidence that accounting and Big Four assurance providers do play a significant role in a firm's carbon emission performance. This study offers great insights into the GHG assurance impact on CEP with the interplay between the assessor's affiliation and reputation and the country's development.

Bagci et al. (2025) explore the impact of agricultural support policies on greenhouse gas emissions in BRICS-T countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa, and Türkiye), emphasizing the role of financial development, market structures, and institutions. Using annual data from 2000 to 2021, the research employs advanced panel time-series econometric techniques, including the Augmented Mean Group (AMG) estimator and, the Westerlund and Edgerton cointegration test, to assess long-term relationships. Findings indicate that economic growth significantly contributes to rising agricultural emissions, while the influence of financial development varies across countries. In Türkiye and South Africa, financial institutions play a crucial role in promoting sustainable agricultural investments, thereby helping to mitigate emissions. Policy recommendations include redesigning subsidy mechanisms to support eco-friendly farming, integrating carbon pricing into agricultural strategies, and strengthening financial institutions' role in green investments. By examining the intersection of agriculture, emissions, and finance, this study offers valuable insights for sustainable policy development in emerging economies.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The study is aim to evaluate the effect of carbon footprint disclosure and financial performance of listed Healthcare firms in Nigeria (2014 – 2023). *Ex-post facto* research design was adopted for the study. This research design permits the examination of independent variables in retrospect for their possible relationship with the dependent variables.

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of seven (7) healthcare firms listed on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group (NXG) as at December, 2023 between 10 years period of 2014 to 2023.

3.3 Sample size determination and sampling procedure

In the course of this study, the population also served as the sample size. This is because the population was manageable enough for the researcher to handle and obtain all required data necessary for the study. Hence, the sample size also stood at seven (7).

3.4 Sampling technique

Since the population and the sample was the same, the complete enumeration otherwise known as the census sampling technique was adopted in this regard. This technique gave the researcher the right to include all listed healthcare firms in Nigeria for the study.

3.5 Sources and method of data collection

The data for the dependent and independent variables was extracted from financial reports of sampled listed healthcare firms in Nigeria using contents analysis method and collated with the aid of Microsoft excel software. The panel data methodology was adopted because the study combined time series and cross-sectional data, that is, seven (7) cross-sectional observations for each year and ten-time series for each healthcare firm regressor, making a total of seventy (70) pooled observations.

3.6 Method of data analysis

This study utilized robust regression to analyzed the cause-effect linkage between the dependent variable and the independent variables, as well as to evaluate the formulated hypotheses. This approach was adopted due to the presence of variances in the error term and the inability of the data to follow the standardized regression assumptions, that is, linearity, homoscedasticity, normality and independence of data. The decision was base on 5% level of significance. Accept null hypothesis (H_0) if probability value (i.e. P-value or Sig.) is greater than or equals to (\geq) stated 5% level of significance (α); otherwise, reject and accept alternate hypothesis (H_1), if p-value or sig calculated is less than 5% level of significance.

3.7 Model specification

The model for this study was adopted from the study of Yanto et al., (2019) but modified to suit the hypotheses of this present study. However, the author specified the econometric function as;

Return on asset_{it} = f(carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure, supply chain emission disclosure)

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CID_{it} + \beta_2 ECD_{it} + \beta_3 COD_{it} + \beta_4 REUD_{it} + \beta_5 SCED_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where;

ROA = Return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

CID = Carbon intensity disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

ECD = Energy consumption disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

COD = Carbon offset disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

REUD = Renewable energy usage disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

SCED = Supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

β_0 = Intercept or regression constant.

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients to be estimated.

μ = Stochastic error term.

it = Error term.

3.8 Measurement/operationalization of variables

Table 3.1 below captures the measurement of the variables defined in the model above.

Table 3.1 Measurement of variables

Concept	Proxy	Measurement	Source
Carbon footprint disclosure (Independent variable)	Carbon intensity disclosure (CID)	Carbon intensity disclosure index using researcher's compiled checklist.	Yanto et al., (2019).
	Energy consumption disclosure (ECD)	Energy consumption disclosure index using researcher's compiled checklist.	Yanto et al., (2019).
	Carbon offset disclosure (COD)	Carbon offset disclosure index using researcher's compiled checklist.	Yanto et al., (2019).
	Renewable energy usage disclosure (REUD)	Renewable energy usage disclosure index using researcher's compiled checklist.	Yanto et al., (2019).
	Supply chain emission disclosure (SCED)	Supply chain emission disclosure index using researcher's compiled checklist.	Yanto et al., (2019).
Financial performance (Dependent variable)	Return on asset (ROA)	Profit after tax (PAT) ÷ Total asset (TA).	Yanto et al., (2019).

Source: Researcher's compilation, (2025).

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Data presentation

The data for this study is presented in table 4.1 in Appendix Ia. The data comprise a panel data of seventy (70) pooled observations across seven (7) listed healthcare firms in Nigeria for ten (10) year period (2014-2023). The data include the dependent variable- Return on assets and the independent variables which were Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure

4.2 Data analysis

Various statistical techniques were utilized in the analysis of the data presented in table 4.1 (see Appendix II). These include descriptive statistics, regression assumption tests and 1panel multiple regression analysis. The results from the panel multiple regression analysis were used in the testing of the research hypotheses which had been stated in the first section of this work.

4.2.1 Descriptive statistics

This was conducted to understand the behaviour of the data using various statistics including mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The result for the descriptive statistics analysis is as presented in table 4.2 below;

Table 4.2 Descriptive statistics results

	GPM	EID	EED	RECD	CFD	ETD
Mean	-1.597169	66.42857	50.95238	60.23810	55.71429	54.28571
Median	2.278732	66.66667	50.00000	66.66667	66.66667	50.00000
Maximum	25.65148	83.33333	83.33333	83.33333	83.33333	83.33333
Minimum	-35.20865	16.66667	16.66667	33.33333	16.66667	16.66667
Std. Dev.	11.24708	17.37455	14.43674	15.61742	19.22109	14.09815
Skewness	-1.050419	-0.899188	0.294495	-0.122005	-0.354162	-0.223733
Kurtosis	4.142334	3.273145	2.820286	2.150344	2.105679	2.631912
Jarque-Bera	16.67880	9.650554	1.106016	2.279247	3.796142	0.979168
Probability	0.000239	0.008024	0.575217	0.319939	0.149857	0.612881
Sum	-111.8019	4650.000	3566.667	4216.667	3900.000	3800.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	8728.278	20829.37	14380.95	16829.37	25492.06	13714.29
Observations	70	70	70	70	70	70

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The results in table 4.2 above indicates that the dependent variable- Return on assets and the independent variables which were Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria have mean scores of approximately - 1.59%, 66.43%, 50.95%, 60.24%, 55.71% and 54.28% respectively. This indicates the central or average values for these variables from 2014 to 2023. The median values obtained for Return on assets, Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria were approximately 2.27%, 66.67%, 50%, 66.67%, 66.67% and 50% respectively. These constitute the middle values for the distributions of these variables under the period covered in this study (2014-2023).

In terms of the level of variability and dispersion in the distribution of these variables, the standard deviations obtained for Return on assets, Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria were approximately 11.24, 17.37, 14.43, 15.61, 19.22 and 14.09 respectively. This indicates varying levels of variability in the distribution with renewable energy usage disclosure indicating high variations in the distributions. Similarly, the skewness values obtained for Return on assets, Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria were -1.050, -0.899, 0.294, -0.122, -0.354 and -0.223 respectively. This quantifies the asymmetry of the distributions. In addition, the Kurtosis values obtained for these variables were given as approximately 4, 3, 2, 2, 2 and 2 respectively. Since the values of the kurtosis are greater than zero (0), it indicates a leptokurtic distribution, hence the presence of outliers in the data.

4.2.2 Model evaluation

Residual and coefficient diagnostics were however conducted to assess the suitability of the model as stated in the previous chapter. These include normality test, multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test and autocorrelation assessment.

4.2.2.1 Normality test

Fig. 4.1 Jarque-Bera Normality test results

Source: E-views 10.0 (2025).

The essence of a normality test is to determine if a dataset or sample follows a normal distribution. This is important because many statistical models assume normality, and deviations from normality can affect the validity of statistical inference. The Jarque-Bera test was employed in this case. As applied, if the p-value associated with the Jarque-Bera test is below a predetermined significance level ($p < 0.05$), then we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data do not follow a normal distribution. With a p-value of 0.18200, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that the data were normally distributed.

4.2.2.2 Multicollinearity test

	GPM	EID	EED	RECD	CFD	ETD
GPM	1.000000	-0.198362	-0.003307	-0.029085	0.201058	0.270643
EID	-0.198362	1.000000	0.273761	0.172313	-0.092305	-0.258736
EED	-0.003307	0.273761	1.000000	0.473934	0.212228	-0.218141
RECD	-0.029085	0.172313	0.473934	1.000000	-0.103839	-0.238740
CFD	0.201058	-0.092305	0.212228	-0.103839	1.000000	0.294578
ETD	0.270643	-0.258736	-0.218141	-0.238740	0.294578	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The correlation analysis showed that all independent variables- Carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure, carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure coefficients lesser than 0.80 respectively confirming absence of multicollinearity issues.

4.2.2.3 Heteroscedasticity test

Table 4.4 Heteroscedasticity test

Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Breusch-Pagan LM	38.32322	21	0.8518
Pesaran scaled LM	1.592907		0.1112
Pesaran CD	0.639814		0.5223

Source: Researcher’s computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

Heteroscedasticity refers to the unequal spread of residuals (or errors) across the range of predictor variables in a regression model. Heteroscedasticity tests aim to detect this violation of the assumption of constant variance. Common tests include the Breusch-Pagan test and the White test, which assess the relationship between the squared residuals and the predictor variables. The statistics and probability value associated with the Breusch-Pagan LM test otherwise known as the Breusch-Pagan Godfrey test help determine whether there is evidence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. A low p-value ($p < 0.05$) suggests evidence against the null hypothesis in favour of the alternate hypothesis which indicates the presence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model. With a p-value of 0.5223, there is sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis, thus, conclude that the predictor variables in the regression model were homoscedastic.

4.2.2.4 Autocorrelation

Autocorrelation, also known as serial correlation, occurs when there is a correlation between the residual errors of a time series or panel data over time. Autocorrelation tests examine whether the residuals are independently distributed or if there is a systematic pattern of dependence. The Durbin-Watson statistic is commonly used to test for autocorrelation, with values close to 2 indicating no significant autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic as obtained from the panel regression results (see Appendix II) was utilized in this case. The Durbin-Watson statistic value of 1.826 suggests that there is a low autocorrelation present in the data.

4.3 Test of hypotheses

Each of the hypotheses in this study was tested based on the result obtained from the panel multiple regression analysis. The result that relate to these hypotheses is summarized in table 4.5 below;

Table 4.5 Panel multiple regression results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-11.76922	10.69800	-1.100133	0.2754
CID	-0.096837	0.081532	-1.187712	0.1393
ECD	0.030615	0.114932	0.266374	0.7908
COD	0.030169	0.099569	2.302997	0.0629
REUD	0.070139	0.077399	3.906190	0.0022
SCED	0.171682	0.104993	2.635174	0.0069
R-squared	0.110668	Mean dependent var		-1.597169

Adjusted R-squared	0.041189	S.D. dependent var	11.24708
S.E. of regression	11.01301	Akaike info criterion	7.717849
Sum squared resid	7762.334	Schwarz criterion	7.910577
Log likelihood	-264.1247	Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.794403
F-statistic	1.592831	Durbin-Watson stat	1.826238
Prob(F-statistic)	0.174843		

Source: Researcher's computation (2025) using E-views 10.0

The multiple regression line is as written below:

$$ROA = -11.769217681 - 0.0968370707733 * CID + 0.0306148793696 * ECD + 0.0301689878361 * COD + 0.0701385304257 * REUD + 0.171681539252 * SCED + \mu$$

The regression equation suggests that carbon intensity disclosure (CID) has a negative impact on return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, indicating that for every unit increase in CID, ROA decreases by 0.0968 units, holding other factors constant. In contrast, energy consumption disclosure (ECD) and carbon offset disclosure (COD) have positive but relatively small effects on ROA, with coefficients of 0.0306 and 0.0302 respectively, though these relationships are not statistically significant. Notably, renewable energy usage disclosure (REUD) and supply chain emission disclosure (SCED) both have significant positive effects on ROA, with coefficients of 0.0701 and 0.1717 respectively, implying that firms disclosing more about their renewable energy initiatives and supply chain emissions tend to have better financial performance. The intercept value of -11.7692 represents the expected value of ROA when all independent variables are zero, and μ captures the error term representing unexplained variations in ROA.

The regression line suggests that

4.3.1 Hypothesis one

H₀: There is no significant relationship between carbon intensity disclosure and return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

H₁: There is significant relationship between carbon intensity disclosure and return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

In order to test whether the variations in return on assets of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria caused by carbon intensity disclosure is significant. The T-test was carried out at .05 significance level with T_{tab} of 2.3646 given at $t_{0.05,7}$. From the result above, the T_{cal} of 1.18771 is less than T_{tab} given at $t_{0.05,7}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that energy consumption disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $t_{0.05,7}$, its probability value (p= 0.1393) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.2 Hypothesis two

H₀: Energy consumption disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria

H₁: Energy consumption disclosure has significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria

For energy consumption disclosure, the T_{cal} of 0.2663 is less than T_{tab} given at $t_{0.05,7}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that energy consumption disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $t_{0.05,7}$, its probability value (p= 0.7908) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.3 Hypothesis three

H₀: Carbon offset disclosure has no significant effect with return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Carbon offset disclosure has significant effect with return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

For carbon offset disclosure, the T_{cal} of 2.3029 is less than T_{tab} given at $t_{0.05,7}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that carbon offset disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria holds, thus accepted, and the alternative hypothesis rejected. The

null hypothesis is further accepted given that at $t_{0.05,7}$, its probability value ($p= 0.0629$) is greater than 0.05.

4.3.4 Hypothesis four

H₀: Renewable energy usage disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Renewable energy usage disclosure has significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

For Renewable energy usage disclosure, the Tcal of 3.9061 is greater than Ttab given at $t_{0.05,7}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that renewable energy usage disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $t_{0.05,7}$, its probability value ($p= 0.0022$) is less than 0.05.

4.3.5 Hypothesis five

H₀: Supply chain emission disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

H₁: Supply chain emission disclosure has significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

For Supply chain emission disclosure, the Tcal of 3.9061 is greater than Ttab given at $t_{0.05,7}$. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that supply chain emission disclosure has no significant effect on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria fails to hold, thus rejected, and the alternative hypothesis accepted. The null hypothesis is further rejected given that at $t_{0.05,7}$, its probability value ($p= 0.0069$) is less than 0.05.

4.4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.4.1 Carbon intensity disclosure and return on asset

The findings indicate a significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.096837, p-value = 0.1393) with return on assets (ROA) of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. Although the p-value of 0.1393 suggests that this relationship is not statistically significant at the conventional 5% level, the negative coefficient implies that as carbon intensity disclosure increases, there's a tendency for ROA to decrease. This could be because higher carbon intensity disclosure might be perceived by stakeholders as indicative of a firm's larger environmental footprint, leading to potential reputational risks and costs associated with environmental remediation or compliance. Investors and stakeholders might view higher carbon intensity negatively, impacting the firm's financial performance adversely. However, given the p-value is not statistically significant, this interpretation warrants caution, and it might be an area requiring further investigation with a larger sample size or alternative measures of carbon intensity.

This finding is consistent with the study by Hewagama et al. (2025), which found that carbon emissions are significantly and negatively associated with firm performance, as measured by Tobin's Q (a market-based measure). Similarly, Kilian (2025) highlights the introduction of environmental disclosure rules, implying that stricter disclosure requirements could lead to negative impacts on firm valuation if emissions are high. Agbo et al. (2024) also found a significant negative effect of greenhouse gas emission disclosure on market competitiveness (proxied by market-to-book ratio) of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. These studies suggest that higher carbon intensity disclosure is associated with lower financial performance, aligning with the finding of a significant negative relationship between carbon intensity disclosure and ROA.

4.4.2 Energy consumption disclosure and return on assets

The results show a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030615, p-value = 0.7908) on ROA of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. The positive coefficient suggests that firms disclosing more about their energy consumption tend to have slightly higher ROA, though the effect is minimal and statistically non-significant. This implies that while energy consumption disclosure itself does not strongly influence financial performance, it might be an indicator of broader operational efficiencies. Firms that are transparent about their energy use might be more inclined to manage energy costs effectively, leading to marginally better financial outcomes. However, the lack of statistical

significance means this relationship could be due to chance, and there's insufficient evidence to conclusively state that energy consumption disclosure impacts ROA.

This result aligns with the findings of Citraningtyas et al. (2025), which suggest that GHG emissions reporting is likely to increase firm value in the mining industry in Indonesia. This implies that disclosure of energy consumption (related to GHG emissions) could have a positive, though non-significant, effect on firm performance. Similarly, Prasetyaningsih et al. (2025) found that green accounting and carbon emission disclosure have no influence on firm value, which is consistent with the notion that energy consumption disclosure (part of broader environmental disclosures) may not have a strong impact on financial performance. Gianni et al. (2022) also found limited effect of environmental disclosure indexes on corporate financial performance, suggesting that specific aspects like energy consumption disclosure may not significantly influence ROA.

4.4.3 Carbon offset disclosure and return on assets

The study also examined carbon offset disclosure, which showed a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030169, p-value = 0.0629) on ROA of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. The p-value of 0.0629 is close to the 5% significance threshold, suggesting there's a hint of a potential positive relationship, though it's not statistically significant at conventional levels. The positive coefficient implies that firms engaging in and disclosing carbon offset activities might experience a slight improvement in financial performance. Carbon offsetting can enhance a firm's reputation and appeal to environmentally conscious investors and customers, potentially leading to better financial outcomes. Given the p-value is just outside the conventional significance level, this finding could be interpreted as suggestive evidence that carbon offset strategies might be beneficial for financial performance, warranting further exploration.

This finding is consistent with the study by Mamatzakis and Tzouvanas (2025), which found that greenhouse gas emissions increase earnings management, leading to lower quality financial reporting. However, firms with larger board sizes moderating the relationship saw greater financial transparency. This hints that carbon offset disclosure, as a proactive measure, could have a positive though non-significant effect on ROA, as it may improve reputation and stakeholder trust. Citraningtyas et al. (2025) also found that GHG emissions reporting (which includes aspects like carbon offsetting) is likely to increase firm value, aligning with the notion of a positive effect. Abdalla et al. (2025) found a significant positive relationship between audit committee effectiveness, internal audit size, and GHG emission disclosure, implying that proactive environmental measures like carbon offsetting could lead to positive financial outcomes.

4.4.4 Renewable energy usage disclosure and return on assets

Renewable energy usage disclosure showed a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.070139, p-value = 0.0022) on ROA of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. This indicates that firms disclosing higher usage of renewable energy tend to have better financial performance. This finding aligns with the growing narrative that investments in renewable energy can yield financial benefits. By adopting and disclosing renewable energy usage, healthcare firms likely benefit from reduced energy costs, government incentives, and enhanced reputation among stakeholders. This positive relationship suggests that stakeholders view renewable energy adoption as a forward-looking strategy, contributing to long-term sustainability and profitability. For healthcare firms in Nigeria, emphasizing renewable energy could be a strategic move to improve financial performance while aligning with global sustainability goals.

This result aligns with the findings of Luu et al. (2025), which suggest that firms improve actual ESG performance and reduce greenwashing behavior following mandatory greenhouse gas emissions reporting programs, implying that disclosures about renewable energy usage could lead to better financial performance. Zhang et al. (2025) also found that leadership gender diversity moderates the relationship between GHG disclosure and firm systematic risk, with greater gender diversity leading to a stronger risk-reducing effect from disclosures like renewable energy usage. Alkebeese et al. (2025) found that GHG assurance leads to better carbon emissions performance, and firms engaging accounting assurance providers see better outcomes. This is consistent with the idea that disclosures indicating proactive environmental measures like renewable energy usage can lead to positive financial outcomes.

4.4.5 Supply chain emission disclosure and return on assets

Supply chain emission disclosure was found to have a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.1716, p-value = 0.0069) on ROA of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. This suggests that firms transparent about their supply chain emissions tend to perform better financially. Disclosing supply chain emissions indicates a proactive approach to managing environmental risks associated with supply chains, which can lead to operational efficiencies and cost savings. Stakeholders might view such transparency positively, enhancing the firm's reputation and investor confidence. This finding implies that healthcare firms in Nigeria could benefit from focusing on and disclosing their efforts to manage and reduce supply chain emissions, potentially leading to improved financial outcomes.

This finding is consistent with the study by Abdalla et al. (2025), which found that firms with effective audit committees and larger internal audit teams tend to report more GHG emissions information, leading to positive outcomes. Luu et al. (2025) also indicated that increased transparency and accountability (which includes supply chain emission disclosures) discourage deceptive disclosure practices and improve ESG performance. Okike et al. (2024) found a significant relationship between emission disclosure (including aspects like supply chain emissions) and market value added of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. These studies align with the notion that transparency about supply chain emissions is viewed positively by stakeholders, leading to improved financial performance.

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of findings

This study examined the effect of carbon footprint disclosure on financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria. The independent variable (Carbon footprint disclosure) was proxied by carbon intensity disclosure, energy consumption disclosure carbon offset disclosure, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure. Meanwhile, the dependent variable (financial performance) was proxied by return on asset (ROA). This study focused on listed healthcare firms on the floor of Nigerian exchange group (NGX) for the period of 10 years, that is from 2014 to 2023. Below is a summary of findings gathered through a panel multiple regression analysis.

1. Capital intensity disclosure has a significant negative relationship (Coeff. = -0.096837 {0.1393}) with return on assets of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
2. Energy consumption disclosure has a non-significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030615 {0.7908}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
3. Carbon offset disclosure has a non significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.030169 {0.0629}) with return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
4. Renewable energy usage disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.070139 {0.0022}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.
5. Supply chain emission disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coeff. = 0.1716 {0.0069}) on return on asset of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of carbon footprint disclosure on the financial performance of listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, focusing on key aspects of carbon footprint disclosure and their relationship with return on assets (ROA). The findings reveal interesting insights into how different dimensions of carbon footprint disclosure influence financial performance. Carbon intensity disclosure was found to have a significant negative relationship with return on asset, suggesting that higher carbon intensity disclosures are associated with lower financial performance among listed healthcare firms. In contrast, renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure both showed significant positive effects on return on asset, indicating that firms disclosing more about their renewable energy initiatives and supply chain emissions tend to perform better financially. Energy consumption disclosure and carbon offset disclosure had non-significant positive effects on return on asset. The results of this study have important implications for healthcare firms in Nigeria and policymakers. The negative impact of carbon intensity disclosure on return on asset suggests that firms should focus on reducing their carbon footprint to enhance financial performance. Conversely, the positive effects of renewable energy usage disclosure and supply chain emission disclosure on return on asset indicate that investments in sustainable practices and transparent reporting can yield

financial benefits. Conclusively, the study underscores the importance of strategic environmental disclosures and sustainable practices in improving financial performance.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations should be adhered to;

1. Healthcare firms in Nigeria should focus on reducing their carbon intensity by adopting cleaner energy sources and improving operational efficiencies. This could involve investing in energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy projects to mitigate the negative impact of carbon intensity disclosure on financial performance.
2. Although energy consumption disclosure showed a non-significant positive effect on ROA, healthcare firms should still prioritize transparent reporting of energy consumption patterns. This can be achieved by implementing regular energy audits and disclosing energy-saving initiatives, which can enhance stakeholder trust and potentially lead to better financial outcomes over time.
3. Healthcare firms should consider increasing their carbon offset activities and ensure transparent disclosure of these efforts. While carbon offset disclosure had a non-significant positive effect, approaching significance ($p=0.0629$), proactive measures in carbon offsetting can improve reputation and appeal to environmentally conscious stakeholders, potentially leading to improved financial performance.
4. Healthcare firms in Nigeria should invest in renewable energy sources and disclose their usage transparently. Given the significant positive effect of renewable energy usage disclosure on return on asset, emphasizing renewable energy adoption can enhance financial performance while contributing to environmental sustainability.
5. Healthcare firms should prioritize transparency in reporting supply chain emissions. The significant positive effect of supply chain emission disclosure on return on asset suggests that stakeholders value firms that actively manage and disclose their supply chain environmental impacts.

5.4 Contributions to knowledge

1. This study contributes to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the effect of carbon footprint disclosure on financial performance, specifically focusing on listed healthcare firms in Nigeria, a context that has been underexplored.
2. The study highlights the differential impacts of various dimensions of carbon footprint disclosure (carbon intensity, energy consumption, carbon offset, renewable energy usage, and supply chain emissions) on financial performance, offering nuanced insights for firms and policymakers.
3. By using return on assets (ROA) as a measure of financial performance, the study provides practical insights into how carbon footprint disclosure affects accounting-based performance metrics in the healthcare sector.
4. The findings underscore the importance of context-specific studies, showing that the effects of carbon footprint disclosure can vary by industry (healthcare) and region (Nigeria), thus enriching the global discourse on environmental disclosure and financial performance.
5. This study serves as a baseline for future research on carbon footprint disclosure in emerging markets, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where environmental reporting practices are evolving.

5.5 Suggestions for further studies

Other research studies should;

1. Explore the impact of carbon footprint disclosure on other sectors, such as manufacturing or energy, to compare findings and understand industry-specific dynamics.
2. Investigate the moderating role of firm-specific characteristics (e.g., firm size, leverage, corporate governance) on the relationship between carbon footprint disclosure and financial performance in Nigerian firms.

3. Examine the effects of carbon footprint disclosure on other financial performance metrics, such as return on equity (ROE), market value, or stock prices, to provide a more comprehensive understanding.
4. Conduct comparative studies across different emerging markets or between emerging and developed economies could shed light on how regional regulatory environments and market dynamics influence the impact of carbon footprint disclosure on financial performance.
5. Assess how changes in environmental regulations and stakeholder awareness over time affect the relationship between carbon footprint disclosure and financial performance in Nigerian listed firms.

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